

BM-5102 | ORGANISATIONAL BEHAVIOUR

UBD SCHOOL OF BUSINESS AND ECONOMICS

MASTER OF MANAGEMENT

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REFLECTIVE REPORT

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1. OVERVIEW

I am an undergraduate student from University of Brunei Darussalam (UBD) with a BA in History and International Studies. Before continuing my studies in the same university, I had the intention to take different master's degree programmes in the UK and Republic of Korea; Graduate Degree in Law and Master in International Relations. However, due to pandemic outbreak from China and the difficulties in getting a well-paid job, I end up taking Master in Management (MM) as it offers the management skills and theory for me to apply for my future career. This programme seems to allow me to develop the most required skills for fresh graduates in their job-hunting period, such as interpersonal communication, accounting and finance and researching methods.

Master of Management offers diverse skill sets than what I got from my BA in History and International Studies. MM enhance the theoretical methods that I already had but at the same time gives more such as leaderships, marketing and understanding of how public and corporate works. Coming from BA in History and International Studies, I learn more about how individuals or organisations did the management in the political and socio-economical setting. Still, from MM, I could use the skills I learned in practice as a manager, which is a higher position in any organisations or companies. Hence, in my own opinion and experience in this first semester shows that I could be a better graduate student once I finish everything, especially from the speciality modules.

Master of Management offers various modules, and one of them is Organisational Behaviour (BM-5102). Organisational Behaviour is a core module which offers different theory regarding the behaviour of an individual in work-setting. This seems to be an essential module which will significantly help the master students once they graduated and straightaway working for any organisation. Traditionally while taking master by teaching, the lecture will be based on teacher-student setting, but the way the courses carried out was based on independent learning, where the lecture provides topics and the rest were based on one's personal research. Other than that, there also a group-work setting. The group-work helps me in applying the theoretical learning regarding interpersonal communication which was one of the Organisational Behaviour's topic. They're also a topic regarding motivation. This motivational theory helps me understand one's personal intrinsic and extrinsic views on things. One of the assignments that the lecturer gave was to write a paper of why I am pursuing Master's Degree in Management, and throughout the writing, I manage to express my own motivations with the theory that applies of my own motivations. From this, I learn more about myself and at the same time retaining the leading core theory of Organisational Behaviour for the Motivational Theory.

Moreover, the group-work setting somehow helps me finding a new circle of friends. I see myself as an independent person with introvert personalities. When doing assignments, it is preferably doing it alone, however, in this master's programme, it proves that in some occasions it is required for me to work with others to finish the necessary works. Success can be achieved through mutualities with other group members. I believe this taught me the importance of every individual in any organisations, where every action of each individual affects the performance of the organisations they work for. Therefore, Organisational Behaviour gives me a new perspective on life.

2. THEORETICAL AND PRACTICAL KNOWLEDGE

From every aspect of our lives, there always be a theory about it. Theoretical knowledge is about learning without the adaptation of what we know in our lives. For instances, *why we behave that way? Why introverts want to spend time alone most of the time? What are the motivations of these individuals to be better?* For every question that we wonder there always be an answer for it. For practical knowledge, it is the opposite of theoretical. Practical knowledge is all about application, in this sense, the application of the theory that we studied. It provides a deeper understanding of the theory-based one's experiences.

The pandemic of COVID-19 somehow affects the traditional learning system of teacher-student lecture setting. Majority of the lectures were held online, and only a few classes where we finally met face-to-face with our lecturer. New learning setting seems to be difficult for most of us. Personally, this is the first semester of my master's programme, and it was hard to get a grasp of what to expect from the master level of study. The needs of interaction and communications between the lecturer and the graduate students are vitals.

Initially, it was tough, but as time goes by, I had the motivation to work better in this new learning system. This was stated by Seifert and Sutton (2018) where there is six theory of motives for learning; motives by behaviour change, motives as goals, motives as interests, motives as attributions about success, motives as perceived self-efficacy and motives as self-determination. I believe that I have the motives as goals and perceived self-efficacy. One of the reasons is that I wanted to be successful and at the same time, trying my best to do the tasks given. Through that, I expect to learn new knowledge and applies it in lives. Other students may use a different approach regarding this matter.

This is in line with the theory that we learn from this module known as Maslow's Hierarchy of Need. I can relate my experience while studying this module with this theory. Maslow's approach is a motivational theory which categorising the needs of individuals, which often portrayed as a five-tiered pyramid. The requirements of the lower tier need to be satisfied for individuals to achieve the top tier level in the pyramid. The needs from the lower bottom tier to the top upper tier are; physiological, safety, love (belonging), esteem and self-actualisation (Schermerhorn, 2013).

Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs

(Fig. 1) Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs, source: simplypsychology.org

Below is a table based on the original Maslow's hierarchical of needs in relations with the hierarchal needs of the students' motivation which can be applied while studying in this Master of Management programme;

What satisfies higher-tier needs?	
Self-actualisation Needs	"What a man can be, he must be" An individual acceptance of what he/she perceived. E.g. Manage to get good grades = being a successful student in the module.
Esteem Needs	Esteem gain through recognition and praises. Esteem from self-achievement, self-independence and etc.
What satisfied lower-tier needs?	
Love (Belongingness)/ Social Needs	Having new circles, interactions and support from other beings which helps one's growth in studying. Having support from family members and lecturers in pursuing a master's degree.
Safety Needs	Feeling secure in the study environment, future employability, study resources and proper internet connections.
Physiological Needs	Internet for online learning, food and water while studying.

(Fig 2.) Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs based on the student's motivation

3. INDIVIDUAL OPINIONS AND PERSONAL CONTRIBUTIONS ON THE GROUP ASSIGNMENTS

As part of the module assignments, I was allowed to choose two random members to be with. The group case study requires research work based on the listed topics given the lecturer of the modules. My groups consist of three people, including me, choose a topic regarding an employee involvement project in Brunei. In our first discussion as a group, we discuss the potential companies to pick, and we listed several companies and organisation. Among those listed companies, we decided to pick hotel management. We created several possible interview questions for at least 20 employees in one of Brunei's hotels located in Gadong.

However, the research was cancelled due to the fact of study that requires primary data collection needs more time than just a semester. It was officially stated by the Dean of School of Business and Economics.

As a result, we decided to do a systematic literature review, and my part was doing research on Trinidad and Tobago's hospitality sectors regarding their differences between the two islands. The others did the same in different countries. Finally, we able to compile our research literature review as one. Initially, it was hard to find employee involvement in other countries as it requires more time for me to look and at the same time skimming through articles in several scholarly websites. Most of the websites are locked and requires a paid membership to read and download. I had to drive to the university which took me at least 30 minutes from my house, just to get access for the sites with the university's wifi. After tens of lengthy article journals, I decided to choose Trinidad and Tobago as that particular journal article was well-written by the authors. I also did proofreading using a premium service for the paper before we submit the work in Canvas.

In my opinion, for this case study group, this research works require more time than just a semester in order for us to finish one research paper with all primary data collection. I experience thesis writing back during my Bachelor's degree, and I believe data gathering itself requires more than a couple of weeks. However, since this research was supposed to be done in groups, the probability of it being finish before the submission date is medium to high.

4. OPINIONS OF THE TEAM MEMBERS ON THE GROUP ASSIGNMENT

For the group assignment, the other team members have done the same as me. Each of us has our own pace while doing this group work. One being "chill" and the other being "faster" which also handle the technical things such as creating docs and provide some insight or new ideas. Whenever there are problems each of us encountered, we asked each other through online communication, and sometimes we occasionally meet at the university and cafes. We exchange some opinions regarding some of the points that each of us does. As everyone has their own views and ideas, many different perspectives and solutions can be used for the research literature review.

5. OUTCOMES OF THE GROUP ASSIGNMENT

The actual group case study was a failure. One of the main reasons was timing as our group did not get the right timing in getting both approval from the university's ethics committees and the hotel's management.

The actual group case study involves us to find out how an organisation controls its employees either in the public or private sector. However, our group decided to focus on employee involvement programs in the hospitality side with a focus on hotels. Employee involvement programs are determined by many variables that encourage employees to participate more such as decision-making, communication, motivation and good relationships with managers or superiors. As the format was changed to systematic literature review we able to relates the outcomes based on different country hotels and then connects it with Brunei hotel's management as there is lack of studies regarding employee involvement in Brunei, the objectives to study the employee engagement programs are;

1. To identify how employee involvement programs work in the hospitality sector with a focus in hotels. To learn essential skills that employees can acquire through work engagements such as communication and decision-making.
2. To understand the rewards and challenges of employees' engagement at work.
3. To understand case studies of foreign countries that see the successes and issues of the programs that can apply to Brunei's employee involvement programs in the hospitality sector (hotels).

Nonetheless, this study met the objectives as we able to find and analysis through the objectives listed above.

6. INDIVIDUAL STRENGTHS AND WEAKNESSES

Upon experiencing this module with both individual and group assignments, I figured out my strengths and weaknesses in learning this module. One of my strength is that I am able to read and understand the articles faster. From this, I able to gather data and resources more quickly. This trait probably developed during my bachelor's degree study as it requires hundreds of hours of readings for a semester and the needs to critically analyse the world's situations in the past and the presents. My strength also interconnects with my interest. If I did not have any interest in the subjects, I would not be able to grasp more knowledge from it unless I force myself into it. I struggle for the past few weeks to a couple of months doing other modules assignments as it requires more time all together. Sometimes, I end up procrastinating as I was not able to cope with the immense amount of work and assignments.

For my weakness, I could describe myself as "ambivalent" when I am caught between multiple choices in a making decision especially when I could not think any of it works well for me and others unless being convinced. This is a trait that I could not able to get rid off, especially when doing group-work. Another word for this is "indecisive".

I also learned that before, while doing my bachelor's degree that I tended to be more autocratic in my leadership style, and this somehow affect my relations with other team members. Hence, for this group works, I tend to listen more than giving more instruction. Thus our group seems to be leaderless and none to lead the group well as none of the team members voluntarily became a leader, but somehow we manage to finish the group assignments before the due dates.

7. RECOMMENDATION AND CHANGES

In my opinion, group work with fewer members is essential for personal growth. As each member may able to gain more and better tacit knowledge of each individuals speciality. Applying tacit can be really difficult as it may not be able to be taught to others but show. Therefore, fewer members the better.

Another recommendation would be having a leader to lead the group work and to represent the members. Having no leader for our group was a significant problem as the members tend to be swayed with other modules assignments and forgotten this module assignments. Understandably, each member has their own pace and with tights schedules, but having a leadership would change the pace of the group's performance.

8. SIGNIFICANCE OF THE REFLECTIVE REPORT

The reflective report can be useful to analyse our own experiences at the end of the semester. It reflects what had been done by practical and applies the theory of what we already learn in the semester. From this reflective, it stated the problems that I experienced while doing the group-work assignments and had suggested the needs to appoint a leader when doing such assignments. Hence, not only it is useful for me to reflect back, but it may also help the readers for their future in case they encounter similar situations.

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